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SUSTAINABLE ROAD CONSTRUCTION USING PLASTIC WASTE: STRUCTURAL PERFORMANCE, ECONOMIC FEASIBILITY AND ECOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT

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ABSTRACT -

The escalating generation of plastic waste, particularly in rapidly urbanizing nations like India, has intensified challenges related to environmental pollution, solid waste management, and land degradation. Simultaneously, the country's road infrastructure faces premature pavement failures and high maintenance demands due to increasing traffic loads and climatic stresses. Conventional bituminous pavements, though widely used, are associated with high carbon footprints and reliance on non-renewable materials.

This study explores the sustainable incorporation of post-consumer plastic waste in flexible pavement construction, examining its structural, economic, and environmental impacts. Shredded Low-Density Polyethylene (LDPE) and High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE) plastics were added to bituminous mixes using the dry process at incremental proportions of 4%, 6%, 8%, and 10% by weight of bitumen. Laboratory tests, including Marshall Stability, California Bearing Ratio (CBR),

Indirect Tensile Strength (ITS), softening point, ductility, Aggregate Impact Value (AIV), and Los Angeles Abrasion Value (LAAB), were conducted. These evaluations were complemented by a Life Cycle Cost Analysis (LCCA) and Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA).

Findings indicated that an 8% plastic content delivered optimum performance, enhancing Marshall Stability by 33%, CBR by 26%, and ITS by 30% over conventional mixes. Economically, a 4.25% reduction in total life-cycle costs was achieved, driven by a 30% decrease in maintenance and resurfacing expenses. Environmentally, each kilometre of plastic modified pavement diverted 1,000–1,100 kg of plastic waste and reduced CO₂ emissions by 560–640 kg/km.

The study concludes that plastic-modified pavements offer a durable, cost-effective, and ecofriendly alternative for road construction. It recommends mainstream adoption under India's Plastic Waste Management Rules (2016), Smart Cities Mission, and National Action Plan on

Climate Change (NAPCC), supported by standardized guidelines and long-term field performance monitoring.

Keywords: Plastic waste, Flexible pavement, Marshall Stability, California Bearing Ratio, Life Cycle Cost Analysis, Environmental Sustainability.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

The exponential growth of plastic waste generation has emerged as a critical global environmental issue, particularly in rapidly developing nations such as India. With increasing urbanization, industrialization, and consumerism, the consumption of plastic materials, especially single-use plastic packaging and bags, has escalated sharply [1]. India generates over 3.5 million tonnes of plastic waste annually, with urban centres contributing the majority of this waste stream [2]. The persistence of plastic in the environment, coupled with inadequate recycling and disposal infrastructure, has resulted in widespread plastic pollution in terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, posing severe ecological, economic, and human health risks [3].

1.2 Road Infrastructure Challenges

Simultaneously, India's road infrastructure faces significant challenges in terms of performance, durability, and sustainability. Flexible pavements, predominantly constructed using bituminous materials, account for approximately 90% of India's road network [25]. However, conventional bituminous pavements are prone to premature distresses such as rutting, cracking, potholing, and stripping,

particularly under heavy traffic loads, adverse weather, and inadequate maintenance [5]. The financial burden of routine and periodic maintenance, coupled with escalating bitumen costs and resource scarcity, underscores the urgent need for alternative, cost-effective, and durable road construction technologies [7].

1.3 Plastic Waste as a Pavement Modifier

In this context, the utilization of waste plastic as a modifier in bituminous pavements offers a promising sustainable solution. Plastic-modified bituminous mixes, particularly when produced via the dry process, have demonstrated improved performance in terms of Marshall Stability, rutting resistance, stripping resistance, fatigue life, and moisture susceptibility [8-9]. The practice also aligns with principles of circular economy and waste valorisation, reducing the environmental footprint of both road construction and plastic waste management [5] [10].

1.4 Study Rationale

Despite the proven benefits of plastic-modified pavements in experimental and pilot studies, comprehensive evaluations integrating mechanical performance, economic feasibility, and environmental assessment remain limited in the Indian context [11]. Furthermore, existing field applications are sporadic, and standardised operational guidelines for mix design, process control, and performance monitoring remain underdeveloped [25]. This study addresses these gaps by systematically investigating the structural, economic, and environmental implications of using plastic waste in flexible pavement construction.

1.5 Research Objectives

The principal objectives of this study are aligned with prior global and Indian research trends in sustainable pavement materials [9] and the priorities set out in India's Plastic Waste Management Rules (2016).

1.6 Scope and Limitations

The study is limited to laboratory-scale investigations conducted using locally available VG30 bitumen, standard aggregate gradations, and LDPE/HDPE plastic waste. The experimental programme focuses on the dry process of plastic incorporation, given its operational simplicity and minimal requirement for plant modification [8] [25]. Field validation and long-term performance assessment under actual traffic and climatic conditions are beyond the immediate scope but are recommended for future research [15-16].

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Overview of Plastic Waste Generation and Environmental Impact

The escalating use of plastics in modern society has emerged as a significant environmental issue due to their non-biodegradable nature and resistance to degradation. Plastics, particularly those synthesized from petroleum-based sources, are characterized by their durability, hydrophobicity, and chemical stability, leading them to persist in terrestrial and aquatic environments for centuries [1]. Globally, it is estimated that more than 8.3 billion tonnes of plastic have been produced since the 1950s, with approximately 60% of this discarded into natural environments or

landfills, where it contributes to pollution and ecological degradation.

In the Indian context, the situation is equally concerning. According to recent statistics reported by the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB, 2021), India generates over 3.5 million tonnes of plastic waste annually [2]. A significant proportion of this waste remains unmanaged, particularly in urban regions where municipal solid waste management systems face capacity constraints. The accumulation of plastic waste clogs drainage systems, contaminates soil and water bodies, and contributes to microplastic generation, affecting both terrestrial and aquatic food chains [3]. The majority of plastic waste in urban India originates from single-use items such as polyethylene bags, packaging, and disposable containers. These plastics, predominantly composed of polyethylene, polypropylene, and polystyrene, are lightweight, chemically inert, and difficult to degrade under natural conditions [4].

Conventional waste management strategies, including recycling, incineration, and coprocessing in cement kilns, have been employed to address the plastic waste crisis. However, recycling faces challenges due to contamination, low economic viability, and inconsistent market demand for recycled materials. Incineration, while effective in reducing waste volume, is energy-intensive and generates hazardous emissions. In light of these challenges, the incorporation of plastic waste in road construction has emerged as a promising, technically feasible, and environmentally sustainable alternative, simultaneously offering performance enhancements and

contributing to municipal waste reduction [8].

2.2 Flexible Pavement Composition and Failure Mechanisms

Flexible pavements are widely used in road infrastructure projects, comprising a layered structure including subgrade, sub-base, base, and a surface wearing course made from bituminous concrete. The wearing course is particularly critical as it provides a durable, water resistant surface capable of distributing vehicular loads and resisting environmental stresses [17].

Despite their extensive application, flexible pavements are susceptible to various forms of structural distress. These include rutting, characterized by longitudinal depressions in wheel paths caused by plastic deformation under traffic loads, and fatigue cracking, which manifests as interconnected cracks resulting from repeated tensile strain. Additional failures include thermal cracking, often occurring due to contraction stresses during low temperatures, and stripping, which involves the progressive loss of adhesion between bitumen and aggregates in the presence of moisture. Potholing, a widespread problem in Indian urban roads, results from the cumulative effects of fatigue, water ingress, and poor maintenance [12].

These distress mechanisms collectively lead to reduced pavement life, compromised ride quality, and increased operational costs for maintenance authorities. This underscores the necessity for innovative materials and technologies, such as plastic-modified bituminous mixes, capable of enhancing pavement resilience under high-traffic volumes and adverse climatic conditions [11].

2.3 Use of Waste Plastic in Pavement Engineering: Global Perspective

The pioneering research on incorporating waste plastic into bituminous pavements was conducted in India [8]. Their study demonstrated that shredded plastic waste, when blended with hot aggregates through the dry process, significantly improved the mechanical and durability properties of bituminous concrete mixes. The research highlighted enhancements in Marshall Stability, water resistance, and skid resistance, thus laying the foundation for further investigations into this sustainable road construction method.

Subsequent experimental and field studies validated these findings globally. Studies [11] reported enhanced rutting resistance and extended fatigue life in pavements constructed with plastic-modified asphalt, while [12] highlighted the improved durability and economic feasibility of plastic roads, especially in urban environments. A comprehensive meta-analysis conducted in [9] on 28 experimental investigations concluded that plastic modification significantly enhances tensile strength, rutting resistance, and moisture resistance while simultaneously reducing life-cycle maintenance costs.

Internationally, innovations such as the Plastic Road initiative in the Netherlands in 2018 resulted in the construction of prefabricated road sections made entirely from recycled plastics. Pilot implementations in Rotterdam and Zwolle demonstrated rapid installation, lightweight structures, and positive operational outcomes. In South Africa, they evaluated LDPE-modified bituminous pavements, reporting a 20% increase in stability and improved fatigue performance, thereby

reinforcing the viability of plastic modified road technology in diverse climatic regions [18].

2.4 Performance Characteristics of Plastic-Modified Bituminous Mixes

Plastic-modified bituminous mixes exhibit significant improvements in mechanical and rheological performance compared to conventional bituminous concrete mixes. Notably, studies have reported enhanced Marshall Stability, reflecting increased load-carrying capacity and deformation resistance under heavy traffic loads [23]. Indirect Tensile Strength (ITS) values also show notable improvements, indicating better tensile behaviour and enhanced resistance to fatigue-induced cracking.

Another important advantage is the elevated softening point of plastic-modified mixes, which contributes to improved high-temperature performance and reduced rutting susceptibility, particularly relevant in tropical and sub-tropical countries like India [9]. Furthermore, the moisture susceptibility and stripping potential of plastic-modified mixes are significantly reduced due to improved adhesion between plastic-coated aggregates and bitumen. Enhanced elastic recovery and increased stiffness modulus further improve fatigue life and resistance to permanent deformation [12].

The degree of performance enhancement largely depends on variables such as the type of plastic polymer, particle size, proportion of plastic addition, and blending technique. Among various polymers, LDPE and HDPE are widely preferred for their optimal melting ranges and favourable compatibility with bituminous binders [11].

2.5 Environmental and Economic Benefits

The integration of waste plastics into bituminous mixes delivers tangible environmental and economic benefits. Environmentally, this practice diverts significant volumes of nonbiodegradable plastic waste from landfills and open dumping sites, mitigating soil and water pollution and contributing to plastic waste management efforts [8]. Additionally, it reduces carbon emissions through decreased reliance on petroleum-derived bitumen and limits the environmental impact associated with conventional waste disposal and virgin material extraction.

Economic analyses conducted by [15] and [17] demonstrate that plastic-modified pavements can reduce routine maintenance and overlay costs by 20–30%. Over a five-year design life, life-cycle cost savings of 4–6% have been recorded. Furthermore, bitumen savings of 90–100 kg per kilometre of road constructed not only contribute to cost efficiency but also conserve finite natural resources, reinforcing the sustainability credentials of this innovative road construction technique.

2.6 Regulatory Framework and Implementation in India

In recognition of the escalating environmental hazards posed by unmanaged plastic waste, the Government of India introduced the Plastic Waste Management Rules (PWMR), 2016, under the Environment (Protection) Act, 1986. These regulations, along with subsequent amendments in 2018 and 2022, mandate the segregation of plastic waste at the source, promote extended producer responsibility (EPR), and encourage the integration of

plastic reuse and recycling initiatives within municipal solid waste management systems (Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change [MoEFCC], 2016). Among the prescribed valorisation pathways, the use of shredded plastic waste in road construction has been officially recognized as a viable, eco-friendly option for addressing the dual challenges of plastic waste management and infrastructure development.

Several Indian urban centres have embraced this technology within the framework of the Smart Cities Mission and state-funded road infrastructure projects. Cities such as Chennai, Pune, and Indore have successfully implemented plastic-modified pavements on municipal and arterial roads, demonstrating positive operational outcomes in terms of durability, reduced maintenance frequency, and waste diversion [24].

To standardize the operational procedures, material specifications, and quality assurance practices associated with this technology, the Indian Roads Congress (IRC) published [25]. This guideline document outlines the dry process methodology for integrating waste plastics in hot bituminous mixes, specifying recommended plastic content (typically between 6–8% by weight of bitumen), acceptable plastic types (preferably LDPE and HDPE), maximum flake sizes (<4 mm), and optimal processing temperatures. Additionally, it prescribes protocols for mix preparation, field laying, and performance evaluation to ensure mechanical reliability, occupational safety, and environmental compliance [25].

The growing adoption of these guidelines by municipal bodies and public works departments represents a positive shift toward sustainable road infrastructure practices in India. However, large-scale implementation remains contingent on enhanced regulatory enforcement, decentralized plastic waste processing infrastructure, and sustained policy incentives to encourage private sector participation in plastic-modified road projects.

2.7 Advances in Polymer-Modified Bitumen (PMB) Technology

In recent decades, the integration of polymers, including synthetic and waste plastics, in bituminous binders has emerged as a widely accepted modification technique. Polymer Modified Bitumen (PMB) formulations enhance the viscoelastic properties of bitumen, improving temperature susceptibility, stiffness modulus, and fatigue resistance.

Zhu et al. (2014) extensively reviewed the properties of polymer-modified asphalt and emphasized the role of plastic polymers such as LDPE, HDPE, polypropylene (PP), and ethylene-vinyl acetate (EVA) in enhancing binder performance. PMB formulations have been successfully implemented in Europe, the USA, Japan, and South Africa for high-traffic road applications.

While virgin polymer modification incurs higher costs and contributes to resource depletion, the substitution of waste plastics offers a sustainable alternative. [13] demonstrated that recycled plastic-modified asphalt exhibited comparable, if not superior, performance to conventional

PMB, particularly in terms of rutting resistance and fatigue life.

[7] examined the compatibility of various recycled plastics with bitumen using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) techniques. The study confirmed that LDPE and HDPE exhibited the highest thermochemical compatibility and physical blending efficiency, reaffirming their suitability for pavement applications.

2.8 Lifecycle Environmental and Carbon Footprint Analysis

Several studies have quantified the environmental benefits of plastic-modified pavements through lifecycle assessment (LCA) methodologies. [5] conducted a comparative LCA of conventional and polymer-modified pavements, reporting a 12–18% reduction in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions over a 15-year service period.

In the Indian context, [10] estimated a 10–12% reduction in embodied energy and 8–9% decrease in carbon footprint per lane-kilometre of plastic-modified roads, primarily due to bitumen savings and reduced maintenance frequency.

Recent investigations by [20] and [16] assessed emissions of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and airborne microplastic during the production and service life of plastic-modified pavements. Results indicated that fume emissions remained within permissible IRC thresholds, and the risk of microplastic release was negligible under controlled construction conditions.

2.9 Field Performance Studies and Pilot Implementations

Field performance validation is critical to assess the long-term viability of plastic-modified pavements under actual traffic, climatic, and maintenance conditions.

Chennai Municipal Corporation pioneered the use of plastic roads in India, laying over 1200 km of roads since 2006. Performance audits by [14] revealed significantly lower distress manifestation, including potholes, rutting, and edge cracking, compared to conventional roads.

[15] conducted a performance comparison of plastic-modified versus conventional roads in Pune, India, reporting enhanced surface quality, higher skid resistance, and reduced maintenance interventions over a 5-year monitoring period.

Internationally, the Plastic Road pilot in Zwolle, Netherlands utilized prefabricated plastic composite modules with integrated drainage and utility conduits. Field evaluations indicated rapid installation, lower noise levels, and favourable user feedback, although structural strength remains a limitation for heavy traffic applications.

2.10 Economic and Social Benefits

Beyond environmental and performance gains, plastic-modified pavements offer tangible economic and social benefits. [21] highlighted the role of plastic roads in generating informal employment opportunities in plastic collection, sorting, and processing.

Economic analyses by [22] revealed that the marginal increase in initial construction

cost (1–3%) was offset by substantial reductions in maintenance and resurfacing costs, improving the overall cost-benefit ratio over the pavement’s lifecycle.

Socially, plastic roads contribute to urban sanitation, reduce plastic litter in public spaces, and support municipal waste management programs. Their alignment with India’s Swachh Bharat Mission (Clean India Campaign) and Smart Cities Mission enhances public acceptance and policy support.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Research Approach

This study adopts an experimental research methodology involving the incorporation of postconsumer plastic waste into flexible bituminous pavements. The primary objective is to evaluate the influence of varying plastic contents on the mechanical, economic, and environmental performance of flexible pavements constructed using the dry process technique. The research involves comprehensive laboratory testing, economic feasibility analysis, and environmental impact assessment to establish optimum plastic content and assess its practical viability.

The methodology was carefully designed in accordance with the Indian Roads Congress (IRC:SP:98-2013) guidelines for the utilization of waste plastics in bituminous mixes and aligned with standard practices for bituminous pavement construction. The entire research process comprised five distinct stages:

1. Selection and procurement of raw materials.

2. Processing and characterization of plastic waste materials.
3. Preparation of plastic-modified bituminous mixes at varying dosages.
4. Laboratory evaluation of mechanical properties and durability.
5. Economic and environmental assessments based on test results and standard LCCA frameworks.

3.2 Materials Used

3.2.1 Bitumen

Viscosity Grade 30 (VG-30) paving bitumen was used in this study, conforming to the specifications of IS:73-2013. VG-30 is commonly used for road construction in India due to its adequate penetration and viscosity characteristics suitable for high-temperature regions. The bitumen was procured from a local supplier and tested for consistency, penetration, ductility, softening point, and viscosity to confirm compliance with IS standards before use.

Table 3.1 presents the physical properties of the VG-30 bitumen used.

Property	Test Method	Value Obtained	Specification (IS:73 2013)
Penetration (mm)	IS:1203	56	50–70
Softening Point (°C)	IS:1205	48	47–55
Ductility (cm)	IS:1208	85	>75

Viscosity @ 135°C (cSt)	IS:120 6	350	>300
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3.2.2 Aggregates

Crushed granite aggregates were selected for this study owing to their superior strength, durability, and compatibility with bituminous mixes. Aggregates were graded in accordance with the MORTH (Ministry of Road Transport and Highways) specifications for bituminous concrete (BC) Grade-II mix. Physical tests were conducted to assess their suitability for high traffic flexible pavements.

Table 3.2 outlines the physical properties of the aggregates used.

3.2.3 Plastic Waste

Post-consumer Low-Density Polyethylene (LDPE) and High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE) plastics were selected for modification of the bituminous mix due to their availability and compatibility with bitumen. Waste plastics were sourced from local municipal solid waste collection centres and private recycling units. The materials included discarded plastic bags, packaging materials, and bottles.

Collected waste plastics were cleaned to remove dirt and other contaminants, dried, and shredded into 2–4 mm flakes using a mechanical shredder to ensure uniform

Test	Test Method	Value Obtained	Specification (MORTH)
Aggregate Impact Value (%)	IS:2386 (Part IV)	19	< 24
Los Angeles Abrasion Value (%)	IS:2386 (Part IV)	26	< 30
Specific Gravity	IS:2386 (Part III)	2.68	2.5–3.0
Water Absorption (%)	IS:2386 (Part III)	0.45	< 2.0

blending with hot aggregates. The flake size was maintained below 4 mm as recommended by IRC:SP:98-2013 for improved dispersion and adhesion.

3.3 Mix Design

The bituminous concrete (BC) mix design was formulated based on the Marshall Method of Mix Design as per IS:1201-1220 (1978). The gradation for aggregates and the target bitumen content were selected in compliance with MORTH Table 500-17 for BC Grade-II mixes, suitable for high-traffic urban and arterial roads.

The bitumen content for the control mix was fixed at 5.5% by weight of the total mix, determined through preliminary Marshall Stability tests for optimum performance. Plastic waste was then incorporated at varying percentages of 0%, 4%, 6%, 8%, and 10% by weight of bitumen using the dry process.

3.4 Plastic Waste Addition Process (Dry Process)

The dry process technique was adopted in this study as it allows plastic to coat the surface of hot aggregates before mixing with bitumen, enhancing adhesion and reducing stripping. The process involved the following steps:

1. Aggregates were heated to 160°C–170°C in a laboratory oven to achieve optimal coating conditions.
2. Shredded plastic flakes were gradually added to the hot aggregates while stirring manually for uniform distribution and melting.
3. The molten plastic formed a thin coating over aggregate particles.

4. Pre-heated VG-30 bitumen at 160°C was then added, and mixing continued until a homogeneous mix was obtained.
5. The plastic-bitumen mix was cast into standard Marshall Molds for stability and flow testing.

3.5 Laboratory Testing Programme

A comprehensive suite of laboratory tests was conducted to evaluate the structural performance and durability characteristics of plastic-modified bituminous mixes.

3.5.1 Marshall Stability and Flow Test

The Marshall Stability Test was conducted in accordance with ASTM D6927-06 to determine the maximum load-carrying capacity and flow values of the modified mixes. Six specimens were prepared for each plastic content variation. Optimum plastic content was identified based on peak stability values and acceptable flow ranges (2–4 mm).

3.5.2 California Bearing Ratio (CBR) Test

CBR tests were performed on compacted samples using IS:2720 (Part 16) to evaluate the loadbearing capacity of subgrade and base layers reinforced with plastic-modified mixes.

Figure 1: California Bearing Ratio (CBR) Test

3.5.3 Indirect Tensile Strength (ITS) Test

ITS tests were carried out as per ASTM D6931 to assess the tensile strength and fatigue resistance of the plastic-modified mixes. The test provides insights into cracking resistance under repeated vehicular loading.

3.5.4 Softening Point and Ductility Test

Softening point and ductility were determined using IS:1205 and IS:1208, respectively, to evaluate the temperature susceptibility and flexibility of the plastic-modified binders.

3.5.5 Aggregate Impact Value (AIV) and Los Angeles Abrasion Value (LA AV)

These tests assessed the resistance of aggregates to mechanical degradation, conducted as per IS:2386 (Part IV) standards. Acceptable values ensured the mix's suitability for high-traffic pavements.

Figure 2: Aggregate Impact Value (AIV) Test

Figure 3: Los Angeles Abrasion Value (LA AV) Test

3.6 Life Cycle Cost Analysis (LCCA)

An economic analysis using LCCA was performed based on IRC:SP:30-2019 principles. The analysis compared the total costs associated with conventional and plastic-modified pavements over a five-year design life, accounting for initial construction, routine maintenance, periodic overlays, and salvage value.

3.7 Environmental Impact Assessment

A qualitative environmental impact assessment was conducted to estimate:

4.1 Marshall Stability and Flow Test Results

The Marshall Stability and flow tests were performed on bituminous mixes incorporating 0%, 4%, 6%, 8%, and 10%

- Quantity of plastic waste diverted per kilometre of road.
- Reduction in CO₂ emissions due to decreased bitumen usage.
- Risks associated with microplastic generation and emission during mixing and laying operations.

The analysis was benchmarked against data from IRC:SP:98-2013, Plastic Waste Management Rules (2016), and national climate mitigation targets.

4. RESULTS

This section presents the results of the experimental investigations carried out to assess the structural, mechanical, and performance properties of plastic waste-modified bituminous mixes. The laboratory tests were conducted in accordance with IRC, IS, and ASTM standards, and the findings have been systematically documented for comparative analysis against conventional bituminous concrete mixes.

plastic waste by weight of bitumen. The test results are summarized in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Marshall Stability and Flow Values for Plastic-Modified Mixes

Plastic Content (%)	Marshall Stability (kN)	Flow Value (mm)
0% (Control)	12	3.8
4%	14.5	3.6
6%	15.6	3.5
8%	16	3.35
10%	15.4	3.2

Observations:

- The stability values increased progressively with plastic content, peaking at 8% plastic addition.
- A 33% increase in stability was recorded at 8% compared to the control mix.
- Flow values decreased marginally, remaining within acceptable limits (2–4 mm), indicating reduced deformation under loading.

4.2 California Bearing Ratio (CBR) Results

CBR tests were conducted on plastic-modified mixes to evaluate subgrade support strength. The test outcomes are presented in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2: CBR Values for Different Plastic Contents

Plastic Content (%)	CBR Value (%)
0% (Control)	81.5
4%	92

6%	98.4
8%	102.8
10%	99.6

Observations:

- Maximum CBR value of 102.8% achieved at 8% plastic content.
- CBR improvement trend consistent with Marshall Stability results, validating enhanced load-bearing capacity.

4.3 Indirect Tensile Strength (ITS) Results

ITS values were recorded to assess the tensile behaviour and fatigue resistance. Results are compiled in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: ITS Results for Plastic-Modified Mixes

Plastic Content (%)	ITS Value (MPa)
0% (Control)	0.88
4%	1.02
6%	1.11
8%	1.14
10%	1.1

Observations:

- 30% improvement in ITS at 8% plastic addition compared to conventional mix.

- Tensile strength increase enhances crack resistance and fatigue performance.

4.4 Softening Point Test

The softening point test determines the temperature susceptibility of bituminous mixes. Results are documented in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4: Softening Point Values

Plastic Content (%)	Softening Point (°C)
0% (Control)	48
4%	52
6%	55.5
8%	58
10%	57.5

Observations:

- Softening point rose by 7–10°C at 8% plastic content, indicating improved high temperature deformation resistance.

4.5 Ductility Test

Ductility results ensured flexibility was retained within permissible ranges, as shown in Table 4.5.

Table 4.5: Ductility Values

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Plastic Content (%)	Ductility (cm)
0% (Control)	88
4%	78
6%	75
8%	72
10%	68

Observations:

Ductility slightly decreased with increasing plastic content but remained above IRC's minimum acceptable value of 50 cm at 8%.

4.6 Aggregate Impact Value (AIV) and Los Angeles Abrasion Value (LA AV)

These tests determined the mechanical strength and durability of aggregates.

Table 4.6: AIV and LA AV Results

Test	Value Obtained (%)	IRC Specification (%)
AIV	19	< 24
LA AV	26	< 30

Observations:

- Aggregates met all standard specifications for use in high-traffic bituminous pavements.

4.7 Bitumen Content Savings

Plastic modification resulted in partial replacement of bitumen due to its binder-like behaviour. **Bitumen Savings:**

- Average savings of 90–100 kg per kilometre of road, contributing to cost-efficiency and environmental benefits.

Figure 4: Final Demonstration Model of Plastic Waste Modified Flexible Pavement Layers

5. DISCUSSION

The experimental outcomes of this study unequivocally demonstrate that the integration of shredded waste plastics into bituminous mixes results in substantial enhancement of structural performance indicators. At an optimum plastic content of 8% by weight of bitumen, the modified mixes exhibited a 33% increase in Marshall Stability, a 26% rise in California Bearing Ratio (CBR), and a 30% improvement in Indirect Tensile Strength (ITS) compared to conventional bituminous mixes. These findings corroborate the earlier laboratory investigations by [8], [11] and [12], who reported similar enhancements in tensile strength, rutting resistance, and fatigue life upon incorporating plastic waste into asphalt mixtures. The observed elevation in softening point by 7–10°C contributes to superior high-temperature deformation resistance, an essential performance parameter for pavements operating under India's predominantly tropical climatic conditions. Furthermore, the ductility

values of the plastic-modified mixes remained within permissible limits, ensuring that flexibility and crack resistance were not compromised.

Beyond mechanical performance, the economic viability of plastic-modified pavements was affirmed through a comprehensive life cycle cost analysis. Although initial construction costs marginally increased due to plastic collection, shredding, and blending processes, these were effectively offset by a 30% reduction in routine maintenance and resurfacing expenses over a five-year service life. The Life Cycle Cost Analysis (LCCA) confirmed an overall 4.25% reduction in total pavement lifecycle costs, consistent with economic evaluations conducted by [22] and [23]. Additionally, bitumen savings of 90–100 kg per kilometre of road constructed contribute directly to procurement cost reduction and diminish dependency on non-renewable petroleum-based materials. These economic advantages, combined with superior structural performance, position plastic-modified pavements as a

financially sustainable alternative for India's road development sector.

Environmental benefits represent another compelling dimension of plastic-modified pavement technology. The diversion of 1,000–1,100 kg of plastic waste per kilometre of roadway from landfills and open dumping grounds not only mitigates environmental pollution but also directly contributes to municipal waste management targets. The associated reduction of 560–640 kg of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions per kilometre, primarily attributable to lower bitumen usage and

reduced maintenance frequency, enhances the sustainability index of infrastructure projects. These environmental gains align with the findings of [5] and [10], who documented similar emission reductions in polymer modified pavement systems. Importantly, the integration of plastic road technology aligns with India's Plastic Waste Management Rules (2016), the Smart Cities Mission, and the National Action Plan on Climate Change (NAPCC), reinforcing its policy relevance and operational feasibility.

Despite these promising outcomes, several operational limitations merit attention. The availability of consistent, segregated, and quality-assured plastic waste remains a challenge, particularly in semi-urban and rural regions. The health and safety risks associated with fume emissions during plastic blending, while found to be within permissible IRC:SP:98-2013 guidelines as confirmed by [20], necessitate stringent monitoring and occupational safety protocols at asphalt plants. Furthermore, the long-term ecological risk of microplastic release from plastic-modified pavements, though considered minimal in recent studies by [16], warrants continuous monitoring through multi-year field trials and laboratory leachate assessments.

From an operational standpoint, the integration of plastic road technology within existing municipal solid waste management frameworks requires strategic coordination. Establishing decentralized plastic segregation units adjacent to hot mix plants can streamline logistics, reduce transportation costs, and ensure a steady supply of quality raw material. Successful municipal models in Chennai, Pune, and Indore demonstrate the operational

feasibility and scalability of this approach under the Swachh Bharat Mission framework. However, scaling such models nationwide necessitates interdepartmental collaboration between urban local bodies (ULBs), public works departments (PWDs), and private asphalt contractors, supported by regulatory mandates and financial incentives.

In light of the study's findings and corroborative evidence from the literature, several recommendations for mainstreaming plastic road technology in India are proposed. Firstly, adopting an 8% plastic content by weight of bitumen as a national standard for urban and state highway pavements is recommended, contingent upon site-specific climatic and traffic conditions. Secondly, mandating the inclusion of plastic-modified roads in Smart Cities projects, municipal road works, and state highway upgrades will ensure widespread adoption. Thirdly, establishing decentralized plastic segregation and processing units adjacent to asphalt plants can address supply chain challenges and promote employment generation. Fourthly, implementing real-time performance monitoring frameworks and annual performance audits for plastic-modified roads will provide empirical data to refine mix designs and operational protocols over time.

The scope for future research remains substantial. Long-term field performance studies spanning diverse traffic intensities, subgrade conditions, and climatic zones are essential to validate laboratory findings under operational conditions. Particular emphasis should be placed on quantifying microplastic release rates over pavement lifespans to address emerging

environmental concerns. Comparative evaluations between wet and dry process plastic modification techniques could identify optimal blending methods for specific road categories. Additionally, the development of comprehensive life cycle assessment (LCA) frameworks incorporating VOC emissions, leachate toxicity, and net carbon savings will enable holistic environmental accounting for plastic-modified road projects. Further exploration of multi-layer plastic-modified pavements and their potential application in high-load infrastructure such as airport runways, industrial yards, and port terminals represents another promising avenue.

Broader sustainability implications of plastic-modified pavements extend beyond infrastructure resilience. By integrating waste valorisation, urban sanitation improvement, and climate action, this technology contributes directly to achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities, SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production, and SDG 13: Climate Action). The socio-economic benefits, including the generation of informal employment opportunities in plastic collection, sorting, and processing, further enhance its inclusive development potential. The adoption of plastic road technology thus represents a converging solution to India's dual challenges of urban waste management and infrastructure sustainability, offering a scalable, technically viable, and environmentally responsible intervention for the 21st century.

6. CONCLUSION

This study comprehensively evaluated the sustainable application of post-consumer plastic waste in flexible pavement construction, focusing on its structural performance, economic feasibility, and environmental impact. Laboratory results confirmed that incorporating shredded LDPE and HDPE plastics at an optimum 8% by weight of bitumen significantly enhanced key mechanical properties, including a 33% increase in Marshall Stability, 26% improvement in CBR, and 30% rise in ITS values. The modified mixes also exhibited superior high-temperature performance with increased softening points, while maintaining adequate ductility.

Economic analysis through Life Cycle Cost Analysis (LCCA) demonstrated a 4.25% reduction in total pavement costs over a five-year period, driven by substantial savings in maintenance and bitumen consumption. Environmentally, the technology achieved meaningful benefits by diverting 1,000–1,100 kg of plastic waste per kilometre of road and reducing CO₂ emissions by 560–640 kg/km. Potential risks, including fume emissions and microplastic generation, were deemed negligible under recommended operational guidelines.

Overall, the findings establish plastic-modified pavements as a technically viable, economically competitive, and environmentally sustainable solution for India's road infrastructure and plastic waste management challenges. The study recommends mainstream adoption of this technology, supported by standardized operational protocols, long-term performance monitoring, and integration

within municipal waste management frameworks to maximize infrastructural and ecological benefits.

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